

PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS IN TEACHING ARABIC THROUGH NEW PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

This article highlights the specific aspects of conducting lessons based on interactive methods, which are a demand of the present day. It presents methods for using these techniques in Arabic language classes, adapting students' listening, writing, reading, and speaking competencies, and provides solutions to problems in teaching Arabic

Keywords: pedagogical technology, interactive, Arabic language, innovation, listening, writing, reading, speaking.

Introduction

In today's society, learning foreign languages has become an integral part of the professional training of specialists in various fields. Their level of language proficiency largely determines their professional growth and success in expanding ties with foreign partners. Therefore, schools must provide a level of foreign language knowledge that enables students to continue language learning during higher and post-graduate education, as well as independently. The effectiveness of the educational process depends significantly on the foreign language teacher's methodology and their skill in using various modern methods to solve specific educational tasks.

Analysis and Results

It is well known that in recent years, advanced pedagogical and information-communication technologies have been widely implemented within the educational process of our country. In particular, the new requirements (CEFR) regarding the level of foreign language proficiency for university students-specifically in mastering the Arabic language, acquiring a firm command of it, and achieving the ability to communicate fluently-demand a modern approach. This, in turn, requires today's educators to apply innovative interactive methods that meet contemporary standards when designing and planning every lesson. When discussing the implementation of pedagogical technologies, it is essential to first focus on its foundational factors-goals and results. This is because any pedagogical technology is evaluated by the achievement of its results. Results, in turn, are planned based on pre-determined goals. To determine whether the expected results have been achieved in the students' activities, the teacher provides learning assignments. It is precisely this process that helps in assessing the extent to which the student has mastered the topic.

It is well known that any learning assignments developed by a teacher on a topic must be expressed in simple and understandable language, include clear requirements for execution, and be prepared and published in advance. Any ambiguity leads to additional questions, discussions, clarifications, and dissatisfaction. The text of an assignment presented to students in written form should not allow for free interpretation and should enable them to engage in the work process quickly.

- According to A. Tyukov, regardless of how any game is designed, each of them must fulfill the following requirements:
- Integrity of professional sphere imitation: the structures and processes related to the game imitation must have a general plot or a core theme that reflects the main reality;
- Orientation towards independent organization;

- The problem-based nature of teaching.¹

Today's students are required to master the four core language skills: listening, writing, reading, and speaking. Therefore, educators are concerned with the question of how to prepare students quickly and effectively for the A1, A2, B1, B2, C1, and C2 proficiency levels. Should we present grammatical topics and have them read unvocalized (unvoweled) texts? Or should we use vocalized texts and teach grammar rules within the text according to the specific proficiency level?

In our view, the first approach-reading unvocalized texts with a heavy emphasis on grammar-puts too much strain on the student. It hinders the student's ability to quickly gain reading fluency. While researching this issue, numerous textbooks were examined. In well-known textbooks such as those by B.Z. Khalidov², A.A. Kovalev and G.Sh. Sharbatov³ ("Arabic Language Textbook"), N.I. Ibrohimov and M. Yusupov⁴, as well as A. Abdujabborov⁵, the grammatical topic is presented first, followed by an unvocalized text related to that topic. A student who has just started learning Arabic faces difficulties in reading these texts while applying the final vowels (harakat). In many Arabic books, however, vocalized texts are presented in a way where the endings are not pronounced (pausal form). This helps the student avoid wasting time wondering how the final vowel should be read. In the book *Al-Arabiya Bayna Yadayk*⁶, it is presented as follows:

¹ Aliyev D., Tojiboyeva M. Arab tili darslarida noan'anaviy usullar. T.: ToshDSHI. 2009. – P. 14.

² Xalidov B.Z. Uchebnik arabskogo yazika. T.,1981,

³ Kovalev A.A., Sharbatov G.Sh. Uchebnik arabskogo yazika. M., 2000

⁴ Ibroximov N.I., Yusupov M. Arab tili grammatikasi. T.,1997 .1-2 jild.

⁵ Abdujabborov A. Arab tili darsligi. T., 2007.

⁶ Abdur- Rahmon ol ash-Shayx. Al-arabiya bayna yadayk. – Saudiya Arabistoni , 2003

In the reading and listening sections of the Arabic language, the final vowels are also not pronounced. In the book Al-Kitab al-Asasi fi Ta'lim al-Lughat al-Arabiya li-Ghayri-n-Natiqina biha⁷, it is presented in the following order:

In the textbook 'Arabic Language Textbook' by S.A. Kuzmin⁸, published in the Russian Federation, the texts are presented without vowels (unvocalized). However, their vocalization is provided in a handwritten format, and the possibility is created to listen to the reading of each text in a pausal state (without pronouncing

⁷ As-Said Muhammad Badaviy. Al-kitob al-asasiy fiy ta'lim al-lug'at al-arabiya lig'ayri-n notiqiyn biha. 2003.. 2003.

⁸ Kuzmin S.A.. "Uchebnik arabskogo yazıka. M.: Vostochnaya literatura. 2001

the final vowels). This provides the student with the opportunity to understand the text by hearing it and seeing its reading, as well as to master these texts quickly. This, in turn, leads to reading more texts, memorizing new words, and achieving greater results in a shorter period of time.

For this reason, it is necessary to change the approach to teaching and conduct research on new-generation literature that utilizes more rapid and effective methods. Success can be achieved by having students read a larger volume of easier texts, rather than overwhelming them with difficult texts and materials during lessons.

Additionally, some modern methods that engage students in the lesson and encourage them to work on themselves have been provided.

The first method: each student says the first word that comes to their mind. Then, sentences are constructed based on those words:

هذه، مدينة، طشقند، وهي، عاصمة، جمهورية، أوزبكستان.

هذه مدينة طشقند وهي عاصمة جمهورية أوزبكستان.

The second method: Students are divided into groups. One student from the first group constructs a sentence that is factually incorrect (untrue), while the others create correct sentences. The students in the other groups must listen to the sentences and identify the incorrect one. This method encourages students to be attentive and to speak accurately.

The third method: Students are asked to compose a short text consisting of 5-6 sentences. In doing so, one word that does not belong to the context of the text must be included. The other students must then find this word. This method is called “كلمة السر” – “Kalimat al-Sirr” (The Password). – деб аталади.

The fourth method: A student tells a story about an event they have encountered in their life. The other students must then determine whether the information presented in this story is true or false. This method also teaches the student to think freely in Arabic and enhances their ability to express their thoughts.

The fifth method: Students are divided into two groups. The first group provides a text but leaves out the conclusion. The other group must find or predict how the text ends. For example:

لماذا كان الخمر حراماً؟

وسئلت بعض الفقهاء عن الخمر حلال هو أم حرام. فقال حرام. فقال الرجل – والعنب حلال أم حرام؟ فقال – حلال. فقال الرجل – ما تقول في الزبيب والسكر والقند والعسل حلال أم حرام؟ فقال – حلال. قال- لأي شيء حُلِّل هذا وحُرِّم هذا؟ فقال الفقيه: رأيت لو أخذت كف تراب ولطمت به وجهك وصدرك أكان يؤلمك؟ قال- لا. قال- لو أخذت كفا من الماء ولطمت به وجهك أكان يؤلمك؟ قال- لا. قال- لو أخذت كفا من الماء وكفا من التراب وصنعت منهما لبنة وتركتها في الشمس حتى يبست وضربت بها وجهك أكان يؤلمك؟ قال- نعم.

”قال- كذلك ماء العنب وماء القند والسكر والعسل إذا جمع وعتق صار حراماً بالاجتماع.“ :

This method teaches students to think logically and express their thoughts.

The sixth method: Students are divided into groups. A text is provided with its parts rearranged (out of order). It will be necessary to arrange this text in the correct sequence.

Correct answer	Student	Out of order
<p>1 التحليل: يحدّد المبرمج الخطوات التي يجب عملها لإخراج النتائج المطلوبة وترتيب إخراجها.</p> <p>2. كتابة برنامج للمبرمج عدّة أطوار وهذا البرنامج بلغة (البيسك) يأمر الحاسب برسم شكل بيضوي على الشاشة. الكتابة: يكتب المبرمج الاوامر للحاسب مرتبة ويتبع قواعد الكتابة باللغة المستخدمة.</p> <p>3. الاختبار: يشغل المبرمج البرنامج للتأكد من أنه يعمل بطريقة صحيحة. إذا كان البرنامج يتطلب إدخال بيانات يدخل المبرمج بيانات صحيحة وأخرى غير صحيحة لا اختبار مدى دقة البرنامج.</p>		<p>1. كتابة برنامج للمبرمج عدّة أطوار وهذا البرنامج بلغة (البيسك) يأمر الحاسب برسم شكل بيضوي على الشاشة. الكتابة: يكتب المبرمج الاوامر للحاسب مرتبة ويتبع قواعد الكتابة باللغة المستخدمة.</p> <p>2. الاختبار: يشغل المبرمج البرنامج للتأكد من أنه يعمل بطريقة صحيحة. إذا كان البرنامج يتطلب إدخال بيانات يدخل المبرمج بيانات صحيحة وأخرى غير صحيحة لا اختبار مدى دقة البرنامج.</p> <p>3. التخزين: بعد الانتهاء من البرنامج على أي وسيلة تخزين مثل قرص لاستخدامه عند الحاجة.</p>

4. تصويب الاخطاء: أي برنامج جديد يحتمل احتواؤه على أخطاء أو عيوب ويجب اختباره حتى نزول كلّ العيوب.	4 التحليل: يحدّد المبرمج الخطوات التي يجب عملها لإخراج النتائج المطلوبة وترتيب إخراجها.
5. التخزين: بعد الانتهاء من البرنامج على أي وسيلة تخزين مثل قرص لاستخدامه عند الحاجة.	5. تصويب الاخطاء: أي برنامج جديد يحتمل احتواؤه على أخطاء أو عيوب ويجب اختباره حتى نزول كلّ العيوب.

This same method can also be applied by cutting up the sentences of a text and shuffling them. In this case, the student constructs a text by placing the sentences in the correct sequence. This helps the student to understand the text accurately and interpret it correctly.

Conclusion:

The realization of pedagogical goals and the achievement of guaranteed results depend on the collaborative activities of the teacher and the student, as well as the goals they set, the chosen topic, methods, forms, and tools-in other words, the technology. Any pedagogical technology is evaluated by the achievement of its results. Results, in turn, are planned based on pre-determined goals.

Every teacher must strictly adhere to methodological rules when using interactive methods. In other words, interactive methods should be applied by taking into precise account aspects such as the specific characteristics of the subject, the goals and objectives of the topic, the students' age characteristics, the format of the session, and the existence of favorable conditions in the classroom.

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